

MUSICAL ATTITUDES IN THE HERITAGE OF MIDDLE EASTERN ARTISTS

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The future of independent Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without young people. The art of music has a direct and strong influence on a person from his youth and occupies a great place in his general cultural development. It is no exaggeration to say that music is spiritual food that penetrates deeply into the human heart. Music is a person's whole life, his constant companion. Undoubtedly, it is true that music has a great role in raising a generation worthy of our ancestors. Education is a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the necessary characteristics to live in society.

Our music culture has its rich, strong traditions and deep roots. As an integral part of world civilization, Eastern national culture occupies a special place in the chain of universal values. Our great scholars who contributed to the development of Eastern music culture, Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Uzlug Tarkhan Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Mansur ibn Zayla, Safiuddin Abdilmomin Urmawi and many other great teachers left an indelible mark on the science and practice

of music. . Our alumni left a legacy of works worth being proud of in the field of music culture. Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Uzlug Tarkhan Farabi, the greatest exponent of Eastern music culture, lived and created in the years 873-950. Alloma was both a composer and a skilled performer of instruments such as oud,

tanbur, gijjak, and flute. Due to his musical abilities, Farabi was intimately familiar with the musical culture of different nations. There are sources and narrations about the fact that Farabi plays music, sings melodies, and has a strong influence on people, sometimes puts the energetic people in a state of silence, sometimes puts the intelligent people to sleep, and sometimes surprises the sly ones. In science, he created works of universal importance and left an indelible mark in the history of musicology. Farabi's works "On the classification of sciences", "***A word about music***", "The big book about music" and many others are mentioned. In his work "The Big Book of Music" he describes his detailed views on the theoretical and practical aspects of music science.

Farabi's multi-volume work "***The Big Book of Music***" deals with harmony of tone, musical instruments known in the Near and Middle East, ways and methods of their performance, and the history of music in general, gave detailed information. Farabi's music is a spiritual blessing that fills the human senses, the spirituality and enlightenment of the innate talents and abilities, and fills the mind and understanding.

For Abu Ali ibn Sina, music was considered both a formative of human spirituality and an ethical and aesthetic criterion of this spirituality. In the introduction to his work "Ash-Shifa", he comments on the culturalization of sound and human senses in expressing human spirituality. He said that one of

the main reasons for the emergence of music is the spiritual need among people, that through music, a person warns others about the events that are happening in his mood and psyche, and because of this, music is related to the cultural life of people. Ibn Sina emphasizes that the art of music is of great importance in the spiritual maturity of people. He understands sound and speech as symbols of human perfection. It is not for nothing that Ibn Sina called his works "Ash-Shifa", "An-Najat" and "Wisdom", considering music as a source of spiritual nourishment for people, and salvation in getting rid of ignorance and ignorance. In addition to his treatises on music, Ibn Sina also presented his treatises on other fields, especially medical science. He writes in "The Laws of Medicine"; "...to strengthen the child's client, two things should be applied to him. One is rocking the baby slowly, and the other is music and lullabies, which are customary to tell him to sleep. Depending on the amount of acceptance of these two, the child's talent for physical education with his body and music with his soul is formed. Therefore, music serves not only to improve a person physically, but also spiritually. The wise men of the East, who gave special importance to the role of music in human spirituality, relying on the educational and educational influence of music, believed that the behavior of the composer and musician should become a criterion of piety, virtue and sophistication.

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